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The Dichotomy of Body and Soul In Girish Karnad's *Hayavadana*: A Study of Padmini's Psychic Turmoil

Rakesh Patel*

The context plays a vital role when we attempt an earnest study of a piece of literature. Girish Karnad's well known play *Hayavadana* requires us to pay a special heed to its context and the present scenario if we really wish to probe into the psyche of a leading character like Padmini.

Though the roots of the play are under the soil of ancient myths and legends, its relevancy is felt even today in terms of the dichotomy of body and mind in which we often caught. In India, the roots of spirituality are deep down into the essence of humanity in general. Even though our body desires something the soul would deny. However, it is the discrimination power which wins.

The main plot of the play *Hayavadana* is based on 'the story of transported heads' in the Sanskrit *Vetala Panchavimsati*. What adds the charm to the play is Karnad's own treatment with the old theme and as a result, what we see is the life-like characters that we come across in our daily lives. The central character Padmini undergoes the same pangs of life and confusion when it comes to making a choice. She is torn between the two choices in terms of Kapila and Devadutta, one is physically strong whereas the other is rationally superior. Since she is very much flesh-n-blood, she desires to have both but this is not possible due to the social restrains. She cannot marry both but the fate makes a miracle for her. Initially she feels to be triumphant for her wish but later on she gets the right impression about the nature that humans are mere puppets to act to the tunes of the nature.

Devadutta is an attractive Brahmin youth with a beauty of the mind. He falls in love with an unrivaled and witty girl named Padmini. Being a son of an ironsmith, Kapila has wonderful physique. Devadutta and Kapila are close friends like two bodies and one soul. When Kapila comes to know that his friend Devadutta is in love with Padmini, he helps him to win her love and finally arranges the marriage of Padmini with his friend. Meanwhile, Padmini

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unconsciously develops likings for Kapila. At a time Devadutta becomes suspicious for Padmini's soft behavior towards his friend Kapila:

“Does she really not see? Or
She deliberately playing this game
With him?” (22)

Devadutta represents the beauty of the mind whereas Kapila represents the physical energy. Being a human Padmini is caught between these two qualities and unconsciously desires both. Padmini likes the simplicity of Devadutta but at the same time she is blinded by the ethereal shape of Kapila. She praises Kapila's body in words as:

“What an eternal shape!
Such a broad back-ocean like
Muscles rippling across it” (25)

Since Devadutta develops an extreme jealousy, it becomes hard for him to live and ultimately sacrifices his life to the Goddess Kali. Kapila also loses his life leaving Padmini to be baffled at such horrified situation. In haste, Padmini attaches the head of Devadutta to the body of Kapila and the head of Kapila to the body of Devadutta. Due to the blessings of the Goddess Kali both come to life but the real problem arises as to whom Padmini should go with. A great Rishi offers a fine solution to the predicament of Padmini and advises her to go with the man with Devadutta's head.

When Padmini goes with the man with Devadutta's head and Kapila's body, her mind fills with extreme joy because she has now both, the beauty of Devadutta's mind and the eternal shape of Kapila. But the power of nature is supreme and unpredictable. With the course of the time, Devadutta gains body of Kapila and Kapila develops the intellectual beauty of Devadutta. At the end of the play, both friends Devadutta and Kapila fights a duel in which their heads roll again and Padmini toys the idea of performing sati.

Like a modern emancipated woman, Padmini's predicament is worth to mention in today's context. She pines for Devadutta's intellectual power as well as Kapila's physical power. She gets the opportunity to have the both but ultimately her triumphant vanishes into failure with the course of the time. Since human beings are incomplete, not most desires are fulfilled. Like Savitri in Mohan Rakesh's *Halfway House*, Padmini wish to be loyal to her husband but can't resist the temptation of the physical beauty of other man. However, there is a sense of repentance in her and this leads her whetting upon the idea of performing sati, like a typical Indian woman, at the end of the play.

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